

Data and Infrastructure as Privilege

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I'd like to extend my gratitude to Sally Charnow and Jeff Horn for the invitation to participate in this forum, in which we not only celebrate the contributions of David K. Smith to scholarship in French historical studies, but we also begin to take stock of some of the emerging trends in digital humanities (DH) research. Standing in March 2021 we find ourselves at an important crossroads. The crossroads is more than just a trope. The pandemic and reckonings in matters of social justice in 2020 have had a profound impact on our families, loved ones and partners, and have shone light on long standing structural inequalities in our world, as they have challenged us to be more compassionate, critical and equitable in our professional practice. Some of us have committed to decolonizing our classroom and to acknowledging that privilege is built into our positions at institutions dedicated to the pursuit of knowledge. For one, the leadership of my own institution--born of a North American R1, yet serving completely different knowledge communities in a context far removed from North America--has pledged to examine the intersection of blackness, structural inequity and global higher education from where we sit in the Arab region, and in so doing to forge a more equitable environment for the pursuit of knowledge.

But the crossroads is also an *infrastructural* one. Even in 2021, I know that some colleagues react dismissively to the notion of research "infrastructure" or "data" mattering in the humanities, and perhaps even indifferently to critiques of the digitalization and datafication of everyday life.¹ In my mind, they do so at their own risk, and that of the profession and their students. One of the most compelling conversations in DH at present focuses on a growing consensus that as scholars and teachers we must remain active in this moment of digital transformation--certainly not the first, or the last of our

¹ By datafication I mean the way that so many elements of contemporary life are recorded, tracked and turned into metrics, the scale of which now has allowed the data of human life to be turned into new forms of value, especially surveillance and predictive analysis. See Ajana, B. (2018). *Metric Culture and the Over-Examined Life*. Metric Culture: Ontologies of Self-Tracking Practices. Bingley: Emerald Publishing.

generation--striving to understand the contours of what is happening around us and engaging with the transformations, constantly striving to recenter our shared values within them.

It would surprise me, in 2021, if my readers claimed that their reliance on digitized resources or on digital scholarly communication had decreased. In fact, I know from my colleagues in libraries and archives that not only has demand for digital resources skyrocketed since last year, but our working habits and modes of communication have begun to shift as a result. Yet, at this juncture with burgeoning new digital practices that, in my opinion, will not simply disappear with a return to work, *structural* and *infrastructural* challenges overlap and even amplify each other, disfavoring certain identities in the world. A main challenge of the humanities in our time, I believe, is to think carefully about global infrastructural difference as a site of privilege, and to act, in collaboration with others, not to bolster the intellectual prowess of the West, but to co-create global humanities using the digital in and beyond the West.²

My reader will inevitably ask why I chose to weave these three topics together-- pandemic, social reckonings and the pursuit of knowledge in a moment of global digital transformation. The argument that I would like to make here is that while DH research and pedagogy does open new, more expansive windows onto the past by tapping into digitized collections, as its practices institutionalize, they also run the risk of binding themselves to the privilege and the world views that shaped the very processes of digitization and digitalization. My paper is not a petition for more digitization of heretofore understudied archives (although that would be wonderful in some cases!), but rather a call for a combination of agility, an ethics of fair cooperation in our methodologies, a commitment to centering new voices in our work and an openness to understanding of how digitalization is unfolding unfairly in our world.³ As we encourage new research agendas in global or comparative humanities, or as we train our students to shape interdisciplinary projects that will define the beginning of their research careers, we need to keep in mind

² Wrisley, D.J. (2019). "Enacting Open Scholarship in Transnational Contexts." *Pop! Public. Open. Participatory.* no. 1 (2019-10-31). <https://popjournal.ca/issue01/wrisley>.

³ The global community of DH scholars has elaborated many different guidelines for best practices over the years, including that of FAIR data (f_indability, a_ccessibility, i_nteroperability and r_euse of data), and yet it can be argued that these "fair" principles are not inexpensive to maintain and privilege Global North communities with the infrastructure and means to do so. See Rojas Castro, A. (2020). FAIR enough? Building DH Resources in an Unequal World. Digital Humanities Kolloquium an der Berlin-Brandenburgische Akademie der Wissenschaften. <https://vimeo.com/445147368>.

that for different regions of the world, as with different voices in society, that digitally-inflected research will not look the same, nor will it always measure up against the yardsticks of Western scholarly production. As the title of my paper suggests, this emergent scholarship will not necessarily be voluminous, FAIR, open, fast or distant, because of real barriers in data and infrastructure.

As I have been asked to include my perspective as a digital scholar who has spent most of his career outside of North America for this discussion, I will straddle Western and non-Western contexts of knowledge in what follows.⁴ As my digital scholarship draws upon mixed methods, I will also provide examples from two domains: *the textual and the spatial*, pointing briefly to how in each, many examples of emerging digital scholarship across the globe struggle to make a lasting impact, whereas others are on everyone's mind. The domain of digital scholarship is a rapidly evolving one, and an increasingly interconnected one, with legal and technical norms that enforce this connectedness. The democratization of some emergent methods are indeed opening new pathways of working with new source material, perhaps mitigating how we view digitized collections as a site of privileged knowledge. It can prove to be quite difficult, nonetheless, to deliver on the promise of decolonizing digital scholarship in North America, let alone in countries with well developed knowledge economies or in under resourced regions of the world, and this because of the high degree of infrastructure know-how and means that are required to produce, and sustain, high quality digital research.

Digitization--the precondition for DH work on the non-born-digital past--is a moment at which materials of the human record are transformed into a format that they can be stored, transmitted and

⁴ I have had an atypical career for a Western medievalist. My AB, MA and PhD come from American research intensive institutions. I have taught in private institutions, as well as state universities in the US. Since 2002, I have held faculty positions at elite Western-styled universities, the American University of Beirut (until 2016) and currently NYU Abu Dhabi. I have had extended research stays in European and North African research centers. My own first forays into digital research were as a PhD student in the mid 1990s, when we were transcribing and marking up witnesses of Chrétien de Troyes' *Chevalier de la charrette*, to build a "hypertextual" edition.

manipulated by a machine, although it is important to remember that the technologies and methods for digitization have varied over time and space.⁵ As a result, the digitized record that we possess at present is perhaps best described as a "variegated" one.⁶ We often associate digitization with the GLAM[R] sector (galleries, libraries, archives, museums and records management) and with large, costly multi-year, often state-funded, projects, although some digitization done in DH is carried out in a more piecemeal manner or on niche topics of interest to the researchers.⁷ Whereas there are many examples of non-textual, metadata-rich, digitized archives, when we think about digital collections we often assume that the collections are also searchable by keyword. Seasoned users of Gallica (or of Google Books, for that matter), are aware that they can search for documents by author, publisher or city of publication, but they can also do so by keyword, and that the latter uncovers a very different cross section of library holdings. Even more expert users of Gallica might know that such keyword search is made possible by optical character recognition (OCR) of those digitized textual materials, although the accuracy rates can be quite low, especially with older typefaces.

⁵ Salmi, H. (2021). *The Digital Past: Sources and Problems. What is Digital History?* Cambridge: Polity.

⁶ In this paper I address scholarship carried out on digitized collections of the human record, although a very compelling argument is made by historians of the twentieth century and the contemporary period that new forms of archiving, remediation, analysis are required to deal with the born-digital evidence and earlier moments of digitization in contemporary history. See, for example, Milligan, I. (2019). *History in the Age of Abundance? How The Web is Transforming Historical Research*. Montreal/Kingston: McGill-Queen's Press and Brügger, N. (2018). *The Archived Web: Doing History in the Digital Age*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press. In the case of non-Western locales that neither have an active history of digitization nor web archiving projects in place, the future of digital history is most certainly an unclear one.

⁷ A fun example might include The Data-Sitters Club, a digitization project of a multilingual series of children's literature for the purposes of textual analysis: <https://datasittersclub.github.io/site/>. A more niche interest is my own Open Medieval French which has converted public domain critical editions of medieval texts into plain text versions and has stored them in GitHub, allowing for maximal accessibility for digital textual analysis: <https://github.com/OpenMedFr>.

Figure 1: B. Pérard's "À la Bourgogne, pour l'entrée de Mgr le Prince dans la ville de Dijon" visualized in the Gallica interface. Bibliothèque nationale de France, département Littérature et art, YE-3879; <http://catalogue.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/cb31078858d>.

We take keyword searches for granted, since for majority Western languages, OCR technologies have existed for many decades, even though enterprise solutions are hardly a match for the complexities of historical documentation.⁸ The obvious benefits of digitized text are threefold: they are useful for finding material on desired subjects for human reading, they increase the discoverability of the documents as data on the web, but they can also form a corpus for computer-assisted reading, although for the techniques for the latter need to be adapted to particularities of the corpus, such a language or error rate.⁹

In my first set of examples about textual materials, allow me to mention a few collections of Arabic texts that provide some insight into the differences in the ways that digital textual scholarship in different parts of the world can move forward. A trove of books, now known as Al-Maktaba al-Shāmila, related to Islamic studies came online in 2005 and has increased in size ever since.¹⁰ It consists of a large body of plain-text documents, similar to what shows up in the "version texte (OCR)" window of Gallica,

⁸ Smith, D. and Cordell, R. (2019). A Research Agenda for Historical Multilingual Optical Character Recognition. <https://ocr.northeastern.edu/report/>; Cordell, R. (2017). 'Q i-jtb the Raven': Taking Dirty OCR Seriously. *Book History*; Alpert-Abrams, H. (2016). Machine Reading the Primeros Libros. *Digital Humanities Quarterly* 10 (4). <http://www.digitalhumanities.org/dhq/vol/10/4/000268/000268.html>.

⁹ Eder, M. (2013). Does size matter? Authorship attribution, small samples, big problem. *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities*, 30, 167–182.

¹⁰ Verkinderen, P. (2020). Al-Maktaba al-Shāmila: a short history. *Kitab Project* <http://kitab-project.org/2020/12/03/al-maktaba-al-shamila-a-short-history/>.

but much more human effort has obviously been put into making clean text for human reading. There are many differences between Gallica and Al-Maktaba al-Shāmila, not the least of which is the institutional legitimacy of the BnF over "al-akh Nafi (brother Nafi)", the shadow self-publisher of the latter. Furthermore, the publication of the plain text in Al-Maktaba al-Shāmila is removed from digitized copies of the text, making it very difficult to form an expert opinion about their reliability. This problem of so-called "gray literature" (or just gray data, tout court) haunts scholarship in and about many parts of the non-Western world. Nonetheless, the Open Islamicate Texts initiative and digital humanists working with Al-Maktaba al-Shāmila have begun to conceptualize it as a starting point for a future scholarly infrastructure for Arabic.¹¹

Al-Maktaba al-Shāmila is no Google books, since its collections hardly provide a cross section of Arabic publishing over time. Other digital text collections that contain a wider variety of scanned Arabic books include the HathiTrust (HT), Arabic Collections Online (ACO) and the Qatar Digital Library (QDL). In none of these libraries, however, is the plain text available for the Arabic collections in the way that it is for French in Gallica. The reason for this is no doubt the persistent lag in OCR technologies for Arabic, the lack of inexpensive alternative strategies for text creation and the scarcity of scholarly funding in this domain. This means that unlike Gallica, users of Arabic Collections Online can only search in metadata, without the keyword search that the researching public has grown used to in a post-Google Books era. Texts are more readable and accessible than they were in the past, it is true, but the full potential of digital scholarship with these texts in Arabic is impossible to realize in their current state.

Emergent machine-learning approaches are beginning to provide a way to transform such collections that are "stuck" at the stage of pdf delivery. Using Transkribus, a platform that allows for the recognition, transcription and search of historical documents, and building on initial work done by colleagues in Oriental studies,¹² I have been collaborating with researchers to create a machine learning

¹¹ Grallert, T. (2016). The journal al-Muqtabas between Shamela.ws, HathiTrust, and GitHub: producing open, collaborative, and fully-referenceable digital editions of early Arabic periodicals – with almost no funds. Digital Humanities 2016: Conference Abstracts. Kraków: Jagiellonian University & Pedagogical University.

¹² I am grateful to Sinai Rusinek, Adam Mesteyan and Till Grallert for the initial model based on several dozens of pages of ground truth from late 19th century printed texts from Egypt.

model that can recognize and transcribe Arabic with very low character rates for different fonts and typographical conventions.

Figure 2: A page of a printed sixteenth century navigational treatise by Sulayman Mahri entitled *Umdat al-Mahriyya* shown in the Transkribus Lite platform with the automatically transcribed text below it, ready for human correction.

The advantage of this text recognition method over OCR is that it is language independent, it "reads" Arabic scripts as if they were any language in cursive handwriting and it "learns" about the representative language of texts with only about 20 pages of human transcription.¹³ A colleague and I have also carried out this process with a collection of Ottoman Turkish newspapers, the Hakkı Tarık Us (HTU) Digital Repository with very good results.¹⁴ As in the case of the Arabic mentioned above, there was much trial and error, struggle with legacy formats and design of creative solutions to make a system function that was not designed to work with the features of this language (and script directionality!). We are not alone in seeing the potential of such technologies for increasing access to archival documentation manyfold, but there are significant challenges that lie ahead in learning how to scale up the process to work with digital collection such as HT, ACO or QDL. In the case of historically underrepresented

¹³ There are examples of models in Transkribus for a wide variety of minority European and non-European languages.

¹⁴ The digital repository can be found here: <http://www.tufts.ac.jp/common/fs/asw/tur/htu/>. See our paper "Automated Transcription of Non-Latin Script Periodicals: A Case Study in the Ottoman Turkish Print Archive" under review at Digital Humanities Quarterly. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2011.01139>.

languages in digital scholarship, however, these methods are nothing less than a breakthrough. The only missing pieces for such archival transcription to become very widespread, in my opinion, are the accompanying technology of easy digitization of documents as well as infrastructures that can host the images and resulting data from them.

Whereas in the HT Digital Library mentioned above, some of the texts are available for download to consortium members¹⁵, ACO and QDL are more liberal about their reuse policies, giving indications of the conditions with which they are providing their collections, such as Creative Commons licenses that make it clear with what liberties scholars may make use of the materials. These reuse policies are more than just legal frameworks. Indeed, they are mechanisms of encouraging scholarship on digitized material and are supported by technical specifications, such as the International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF) that allow digitized images to be delivered to a wide variety of platforms for reuse. The above mentioned examples of Sulayman Mahri and the HTU repository are not IIIF compliant and required a significant amount of pre-processing to manipulate them, before transcribing them. On the other hand, the documents at the QDL are IIIF compliant, and this digital "perk" has facilitated the work of our research group at NYU Abu Dhabi (OpenGulf) in being able to borrow high quality scans of letter collections from the nineteenth-century colonial residency of the British Raj for creating ground truth for handwritten text recognition (HTR) of the archive of some 25000+ pages of diplomatic correspondence.¹⁶ Increasingly, digital resources and the platforms that allow us to manipulate them, are becoming interconnected systems. Materials digitized in the past or to be digitized in the future, need to incorporate

¹⁵ <https://libraries.indiana.edu/about-hathitrust-etds>

¹⁶ <https://opengulf.github.io/>

Figure 3: A page of a book 46 of the hand copied Bushire Residency Letters (India Office Records R/15/1/19) shown in the Transkribus platform with the automatically transcribed text below it, ready for human correction and machine learning.

these features in order to be equipped for certain kinds of reuse (IIIF, CC licenses, OCR, multi-format export), lest the materials be considered difficult to manipulate and be neglected by researchers. Increasing numbers of digital collections in the West are adopting "collections as data" approaches, by which is understood an approach to digitization that anticipates content reuse for computational study.¹⁷ Such an approach, to repeat the point made above by Rojas Castro, is not free, and it most definitely does form a toll or expertise barrier to digital scholarship in many parts of the world. Whereas the processes for creating data for analysis with digital methods may be democratizing with the rise of AI-powered methods, the infrastructure and the know-how required to keep them working and sustainable has become the new site of privilege.¹⁸

The second set of examples that I would like to mention briefly before closing come from another one of my scholarly interests: the use of geospatial technologies for creating, manipulating and combining data about the spatial dimensions of the historical humanities. For some time now, I have been interested in the notion of the spatial imprint of literary and historical texts, mapping as a way of determining the aggregate of geographical information found within them, or in other words, pointing to the worldview

¹⁷ Padilla, T. et al. (2019). Always Already Computational: Collections as Data.

¹⁸ I seek to nuance the argument made by Risam against the concentration of the digitized version of human heritage in the Global North, by including the aspect of infrastructural know-how. See Risam, R. (2019). *New Digital Worlds: Postcolonial Digital Humanities in Theory, Praxis and Pedagogy*. Evanston: Northwestern University Press.

that such texts contain.¹⁹ In a paper presented at the SFHS / Georges Rudé conference in summer 2020 I argued that straightforward, supervised machine learning methods can be very useful for understanding patterns of citation of place names in large historical sources. These patterns can help us reframe a historian's methods of sense making across a voluminous text. The end result is a kind of transformation of a text into an atlas.²⁰ Even though the computational methods are not exceedingly complex, the approach itself deserves our critical attention, since, unlike the examples of HTR above that can

Figure 4: A map of places mentioned in Froissart's Chronique (book 2 and 4) displayed on an ESRI map base. Data created with the Humanities Entity Recognizer.

learn the intricacies of handwriting and transcribe text at scale with little error, the method featured in this example uses an active learning strategy that actually requires a significant amount of human input to work across such a large text. In the end, the system does quite well finding place names occurring with a high frequency, but can omit many smaller places that are mentioned less frequently. Bias created by the training data is replicated across the whole experiment. Unlike the HTR, however, these work on a regular laptop and are no doubt much less energy consuming! Whereas the above mentioned example is not perhaps the kind of intervention that we think about when decolonizing our research and

¹⁹ Wrisley, D.J. (2017). Locating Medieval French, or Why We Collect and Visualize the Geographic Information of Texts. *Speculum* 92.S1. doi.org/10.1086/694300.

²⁰ Wrisley, D.J. (2020). Exploring the Geographies of Froissart's Chroniques. *H-France Salon* 12.8(no. 26). <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Q0hrHPoIERS> and the technical article explaining the process, Erdmann, A., et al. (2019). Practical, Efficient, and Customizable Active Learning for Named Entity Recognition in the Digital Humanities. In *Proceedings of North American Association of Computational Linguistics (NAACL 2019)*. Minneapolis, Minnesota.

teaching--usually we think beyond works of the European canon to do this--it is notable for a couple reasons. First, medieval vernacular languages have received considerably less attention in text processing than larger vehicular languages such as Latin. As such, we might think of this example speaking back to computational methods with the tricky orthographic instability of a medieval language, challenging normative assumptions of, and brings complexity and ambiguity to, computing. Second, and perhaps more convincingly, the computer code that was used to work with Froissart was designed to be language agnostic, not really with medieval vernaculars in mind but rather any under supported language. The Humanities Entity Recognizer provides a starting point for anyone working with a small corpus, in any language, to begin entity tagging with no pre-existing data.

Finally, it is worth mentioning another central aspect of the spatial humanities, the world of geographic information systems (GIS) and how they function as platforms for combining datasets and raster data (any kind of geographic real-life description from soil types to satellite images and political borders). As in Figure 4 above, geocoded place names are represented on a contemporary map raster showing the nation-states of Europe in 2020, a fact that for some is an unbearable presentism in the representation of medieval data. One of the ways around this is for research communities to create historical border rasters, although this is a daunting task for the sum total of historical epochs. The DARIAH Geo-Browser offers the possibility of historical border maps in intervals going back to 2000 BC, following the approximate imperial borders that one might find in an historical atlas.

Figure 5: The DARIAH-DE Geobrowser's map raster representing the world in 1279 CE
geobrowser.de.dariah.eu/.

Figure 6: A comparative view of the MapSearch portal for visualizing, manipulating and annotating maps from the National Library of Australia's collection (<https://mapsearch.nla.gov.au/>) and a late 19th c Ottoman map of Basra (Iraq) photographed on the fly and georeferenced in QGIS, (Istanbul, BOA.HH. 18/22) with polygons of tribal boundaries on the central Arabian peninsula. (Polygons: Nada Ammagui)

While a pleasantly surprising addition to the world of digital mapping for global history, the historical rasters of the geo-browser hardly provide the kind of granular information of detailed scholarly work. Again, digital scholarship in certain places of the world have moved to fill that gap, forging ahead in the creation of digital map libraries, and through crowdsourcing, have made their maps able to sit on a geographical grid through a process known as "georeferencing."²¹ In other parts of the world, no such infrastructure is available, and most of the maps are not even digitized.

Again in the OpenGulf research group we are studying different colonial histories of the Middle East (most of the information available in the scholarly record) and one of our collaborators had a map that she found in the archives that attempts to illustrate Ottoman conceptions of tribal borders. It is a map that provides an important counter-narrative of the region to that of the more accessible (because in English and digitized) English-language geographical material. Such a map, once digitized, makes a wonderful building block for digital mapping, in combination with the above mentioned process of extracting place names from textual materials or even a comparative georeferencing project along with other colonial-era British maps. We are using it with the goal of a critical comparison of imperial cartographic shaping of Arabian tribes in mind.

Figure 6 above illustrates the differences in infrastructure available for such purposes, with the late 19th century Ottoman map of the Arabian peninsula (bottom) and a map of the city of Goulburn, Australia in 1955 (top). The MapSearch portal at the National Library of Australia has been set up as a public space for user-centered tasking to be carried out with spatial data of interest to Australian historians. What the OpenGulf group did in QGIS (open-source GIS software) with the Ottoman map--georeferencing and annotating polygons--is not much different from what has been carried out with the map of Goulburn, the important difference being the ease with which the infrastructure has hosted the social process of knowledge sharing and creation. Like the HTR platform and IIF compliant infrastructures mentioned above, MapSearch is a platform designed with more sustainable and accessible community knowledge in mind. In the Middle East, the larger national libraries, such as the QDL and

²¹ Splendid examples exist at New York Public Library, the British Library and the National Library of Australia.

those of the Ottoman archive holding many thousands of maps, have not built in such a georeferencer for their collections, if they are digitized at all.

In conclusion, from the vantage point of DH scholarship, many new, exciting examples of digital history have emerged in the world in recent years. The democratization of some tools has made it possible for research materials to be digitized, manipulated and studied through a variety of new lenses. Knowledge production in digital environments is hardly limited to the ability to digitize, as I have argued here, but also extends to the ability to maintain those resources, to make them available to wide audiences, to provide sustainable access to these new knowledge objects, in a word, to promote them publicly. These are the pressing issues of contemporary knowledge production and ones in which power can so easily be reinscribed in access to archives. We may be able to begin to decolonize the curriculum and our research practices by shifting the kinds of digitized materials we use, broadening academic practices and subjects to include other perspectives than those of the European and the settler colonial, as well as to engage in comparative practices that critique the singular imperial narratives of the contemporary world. As a process that includes the reordering of academic debate and intentionally adding new voices to the existing debates, it also implies changing what we study and reconceptualizing the ethics and perspectives we embrace when learning to read sources in new ways. While I do believe that digital humanities research has a role to play in centering new perspectives and voices in the contemporary university, we also must look critically at how new modes of knowledge creation are vulnerable to reproducing forms of privilege in the data they reuse and how contemporary means of knowledge management guide us toward the research materials hosted and created by the most privileged of institutions. There must be space within digital humanities knowledge production that centers data from cultures not currently represented at the table as well as open infrastructures and perspectives that push back on the reassertion of dominant historical narratives.